

HISTORY OF MODERN UZBEKISTAN**Ramatov Murat**

3rd year student of History faculty of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

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Annotation . This is it in the article , modern Uzbekistan development present stage new values system formation processes , values traditionality and practicality and his young people spiritual education tool the fact that values preservation , improvement and upgrade , new ones Create each one period and society for important importance occupation coming , New in Uzbekistan new values system to the body to arrive of the process features analysis and research done

Key words : of values traditionality and historical , historical memory , to values respect, national development , social stability , social and political basics, economy , market relationships , people value for , spiritual in the field reforms , spiritual education , spiritual maturity

Modern Uzbekistan history , as well as " Modern Uzbekistan history "- this the country today's to the day turned cultural , political and social of changes complicated and rich is a tapestry . Silk the way trade of the network one part as ancient from the roots since , soviet artificial companion state as the most near until history has been in Uzbekistan his cultural to himself feature and national to his mind effect showed serious changes happened gave Uzbekistan in history important from periods one is 20th century in their heads Soviet Union to the composition entrance it has been . This period of the country political and social in the structure significant changes because it is independent Khans from the total the only one soviet to the republic turned . This period in Uzbekistan fast industrialization and urbanization process face gave , this while his economy and in society deep to changes take came Soviet in 1991 Union falling apart since he left after Uzbekistan to independence achieved and state to build and state to build to the way fell This period political instability and economic problems with separate stood because new the government own citizens in front own authority and legality installation for fought However time tooth with Uzbekistan this difficulties overcame past , stable and prosperous state draw took

of Uzbekistan new history determiner from the features one its rich culture is an inheritance . In the country centuries during together living came and mutually in touch has been different nations and religions lives This is diversity country art , music and in literature own on the contrary found tradition and of

traditions to himself special harmony cause released . Uzbekistan of history again one important aspect his geopolitical is important . of Asia at the intersection is located this state long from time since regional politics and of the economy main game winner being came His strategic location him history during different foreign powers , including Mongols and Persians and Russians target turned Last in years in Uzbekistan President Shaukat Mirziyoyev under the leadership of important political and economic reforms done increased These reforms country economy modernization do , state management and a person rights improvement , international community with connections to strengthen directed . As a result in Uzbekistan foreign investment , tourism and trade volume increase , economic growth and to development help gave

Such positive to changes despite , Uzbekistan still wide spread out poverty , corruption and a person of rights violation such as series to problems face is coming Government political to freedom have that it is not and the opposition suppression , as well as unemployment and revenues inequality such as systematic problems that he could not solve for criticism will be done . of Uzbekistan development and welfare on the way continue that it will provide for this tasks thorough management and requires control . In general in general , modern Uzbekistan history of the country to himself special cultural heritage , geopolitical significance , political and economic development on the way continue doing their struggles reflection bringer complicated and charming is a story . This history understanding and appreciate through we are today in the day Uzbekistan in front standing problems and opportunities about valuable to concepts have to be , his all citizens for more calm and prosperous moving towards the future can Uzbekistan Central in Asia state in the north Kazakhstan , in the northeast Kyrgyzstan , in the southeast Tajikistan and in the south Afghanistan with borderline It is ancient to periods go worn to history have of people to live about evidence to the Paleolithic period right will come .

in Uzbekistan the most ancient of civilizations one Sogd civilization is from AD from the 6th century BC to the eleventh century AD flourished . So' gdlar advanced farming , trade networks and art with famous was They are East and West connective Silk the way trade on the roads solution doer role played In the VIII century Uzbekistan islam of the world one to the part became Arabs invasion as a result to the region islam religion take entered . In this period Uzbekistan culture and in architecture constant influence left Somonites , Karakhanites and The Timurids such as strong Muslim empires to the body came Uzbekistan in history the most important of the rulers one Temur Temur

name also known as Amir Temur was Timur in the 14th century kingdom set up reached fierce invader was He is from Turkey as far as India was military conquests , art and to the sciences patronage with famous was In the 16th century Uzbekistan Genghis Khan descendants rule did Uzbek khanate to the composition entered In this period great architecture and lively markets with famous Samarkand and Bukhara such as cities important cultural and economic centers as appear it has been .

In the 19th century , Uzbekistan belonged to the Russian Empire Medium to Asia expansion under Russian control passed . This area is Russian Turkestan name with famous is Russian settlers by hard colony done Railways during this period construction and Russian military garrisons organize done Russian of 1917 from the revolution after Uzbekistan in 1924 Soviet Socialist Republic as short for a period of time to independence achieved Soviet period in Uzbekistan industrialization , rural farm collectivization and mandatory cultural assimilation such as important changes take came Uzbekistan in 1991 Soviet from the Union to independence achieved and sovereign to the state turned . From there since country economic reforms , political instability and a person of rights violation such as to problems face came However Uzbekistan education , health maintenance , infrastructure development such as success in the fields achieved

Today's in the day Uzbekistan is culturally rich to inheritance colorful and live is a country . It is colorful holidays , delicious dishes and ancient architectural monuments with famous Uzbekistan people own history and traditions with is proud and fast changed going in the world his own unique to himself characteristic in celebration continue is doing Summary by doing to say Uzbekistan history own of the people endurance and from flexibility proof will give . Uzbekistan ancient of civilizations from now until now time countless people tests overcame passed and proud and independent state as was formed . Uzbekistan to the future look throws It is his rich heritage and colorful from culture power in getting continue is enough

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